

THE DIFFERENCE OF INDUSTRIALISM AND BUSINESS

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Annotation: This article presents the socio-economic differences between entrepreneurial activity and its essence from business activity. At the moment, entrepreneurship solves existing problems in the socio-economic sphere in society and the socio-economic life of society plays an important role in its development. It creates new jobs in the areas of production, performance of works and services, and provides employment for the population plays an important role in securing and reducing unemployment.

Key words: Entrepreneurship, economy, ownership, sector, state, business, activity, forms

Although the concept of "entrepreneurship" was formed in the 18th century, its evolution continues in our time. This concept was used by famous economists of that time, R. Cantillon, A. Turgot, F.Kene, A. Smid, J. B. Sey and others formed as a result of scientific research of business activity. The concept of entrepreneurship despite the fact that it has been used in theory and practice for almost three centuries, its universal definition has not been formed and its multiple meanings are preserved is coming The main reason for this is that entrepreneurship is a multi-faceted, multi-field, multi-branch, multi-form complex activity.

The growth of ideas about entrepreneurship occurs in the early stages of development of countries with market economies. Was considered the most important description of managerial skills, and the activities of a manager were considered above the role of an innovator. But the transition to a high-tech economy reveals such an interpretation of entrepreneurship, which is mainly associated with innovative processes and their diffusion based on their own innovations or on the basis of attracting innovations in the form of innovations.

Now let's move on to the concepts of entrepreneurship and business. Business There are different opinions about the origin of the concept and its interpretation. The main ones are:

1. the concept of business comes from the English word "business", means "work", and in this sense business is any work;
2. the concept of business comes from the English word "busy", means “busy”, and business in the broadest sense is work, it is understood as an occupation, entrepreneurship, profession;
3. business is interpreted as a crushing field of human potential, a field of competition, a sign of economic freedom, a way of development

Entrepreneurship or entrepreneurial activity is an independent activity of citizens and their cooperatives, which is associated with risk and is carried out under their own responsibility, aimed at generating income from the sale of goods, the use of property, the performance of work or the

provision of services by persons, in accordance with the law. Since these concepts are equivalent, it is difficult to separate them, however, of course, there are differences. According to the size of its implementation, business, as well as entrepreneurial activity, is divided into large, medium and small. They differ significantly in the size of fixed assets, and in production volumes, and in financial and labor resources. Large business is one of the foundations of the modern economy, and small and medium-sized businesses are an important indicator of its development and condition. Entrepreneurship involves one's own business, as this is the basis of business. In turn, one's own business is associated with the danger of losing it and losing the expended intellectual and material resources. For the intensive development of business and entrepreneurship, certain conditions and factors are necessary:

- 1) creative ideas, personal interests, benefits, entrepreneurial ability;
- 2) the likelihood of market expansion or the existence of free space in the market;
- 3) the possibility of increasing profits;
- 4) the introduction of innovations, the ability to economically use resources;
- 5) the possibility of predicting crisis situations and ways to resolve them.[1]

Entrepreneurship is creativity. This is his mission and sign new offer or new offer according to emerging need manifests itself in the creation of harmony (combination) and the formation of a new market through it. So, entrepreneurship is a new proposal, i.e. creates value and adds wealth to the wealth of society.

Another benefit and sign of entrepreneurship is reform. Factors of economic production (labour, tools, new, more perfect harmony (combination) of the object of labor), reorganization of production, structural reorganization construction and reform of the socio-economic system will come. As a result, the productive forces of the world are developing, working interaction of productive forces and production relations improved compliance and increased production efficiency.

Each enterprise is opened in order to implement some tasks, for example, making a profit, creating jobs, improving the industry. In the work process at the enterprise, various events occur, actions are performed, the sum of all interactions is called the economic activity of the enterprise.

The organization of economic activity of the enterprise, which is carried out in the field of social production, is to regulate the processes of production, sale of products, services, works. The main purpose of the economic activity of the enterprise is to make a profit. But other options are also possible - a non-commercial type of activity, for example, an organization performing repair and construction work on its own, providing various goods for use free of charge.

There are several types of economic activity of the enterprise:

- ✓ A household is a type in which only members of one family are involved in the production of goods and services.
- ✓ A small enterprise is an organization that manufactures small volumes of goods, products. One or more people can manage such an economic unit. Typically, such an enterprise employs the head himself or a small number of employees.

✓ A large enterprise is an economic unit whose employees produce products for mass use, use, for example, a joint-stock company. Such an enterprise is created by combining the property values of several owners.

✓ The national economy is a complex of branches of production created on the territory of an entire country, which are interconnected by the division of labor. This species is directed by the state, the national economy ensures the growth of the state's economy, increases the wealth of the people of the country.

✓ The world economy is an economic activity in which there is a close relationship between different peoples and countries.[12]

In conclusion, we note that the concepts of business and entrepreneurship differ from each other in form and content.

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